

THE LINGUISTIC PRINCIPLES OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract.

the aim of this study is to explore significant innovative trends in the system of higher education, the problem associated with improving the quality of professional training of foreign language teachers.

Keywords: learning, communication, technology, education, integration, digital generation, clip thinking, mobile devices.

INTRODUCTION

At the present stage the quality of teaching foreign languages (TFL) in higher education directly depends on the introduction of new generation's technologies, namely, information and communication technologies and the use of their didactic potential in the educational process. The concept of 'information and communication technologies' in the educational-methodical literature refers to different methods, methods and algorithms for the collection, application, presentation and transmission of information using computer equipment and telecommunications.

Schools are provided with modern computers, electronic resources, Internet access. This contributes to the introduction of new pedagogical technologies in the teaching and educational process. It is the use of innovative technologies in English language lessons is the main sign of positive results of creative activity, which entails increased motivation of students.¹

First, it is necessary to note the factors contributing to the integration of information and communication technologies in the educational process: first, the information society, which needs modern information technologies, because every year the amount of information increases, which, according to scientists, has increased by 1 trillion times over the past 100 years, which globally exceeds the amount of knowledge that can be learned by an individual²; secondly, the informatization of education as a whole, requiring the active introduction of modern technologies at all stages of training for the preparation of a competitive specialist, as well as a change in the paradigm of education related to the method of learning and receiving information; thirdly, the particular style of thinking of modern students, which was formed under the influence of information and communication technologies. Regarding the third factor, it is important to note the study of American scientists L. Lancaster and D. Stilman, which analyzes the problems of different generations over the past 70 years, namely their relationship with communication, perception of information, style of thinking, and a typology of 4

¹ Innovative technologies of teaching foreign languages // Молодой ученый. — 2018. — №5. — С. 182-184. — URL <https://moluch.ru/archive/191/48195/> (дата обращения: 14.02.2020).

² G.A. Berulava, M.N. Berulava, "Methodological basis for the development of higher education in the information society and the individual in the information educational space" // Pedagogogy, № 4, pp. 11–18, 2010.

generations: generation, born between 1946–1964 (Generation ‘Baby Boomer’); 1965–1980 generation (Generation ‘X’); 1981–1999 generation (Generation ‘Y’); generation, whose representatives were born from 2000 to the present (Generation ‘Z’)

Since modern students belong to the ‘YZ’ generation, the bulk of this study falls on this generation, which is characterized by virtuosity in electronic technology, are ‘digital natives’ because they were born in the technological world, do not know life without computers, mobile phones, the Internet, comparison with teachers from the first two generations who are ‘digital immigrants’ who remember the pre-computer world³.

Currently, more and more teachers are turning to the communicative method of learning English. The object of this method is speech itself, that is, this technique first of all teaches us to communicate. The long-term practice of teaching English proves that teaching with traditional technologies does not allow developing key, basic competencies in a particular academic discipline, so a drastic reorganization of the educational process is needed. For example, the active use of resources of the World Wide Web by the teachers significantly increased the effectiveness of self-education of teachers of a foreign language. Internet services provide access to the latest socio-cultural, linguistic-cultural and other valuable information. It is obvious that the role of the teacher is currently changing; the boundaries between him and the trainee are becoming transparent, which promotes cooperation. The role of the learner increases, learner participates not only in obtaining knowledge, but also in its search, development, transformation into practical skills⁴.

Life in modern society requires from students such important cognitive skills as the ability to develop their own opinion, to comprehend the experience, to build a chain of evidence, to express themselves clearly and confidently. The technology of developing students' critical thinking involves asking students questions and understanding the problem that needs to be addressed. Critical thinking has an individual character; each generates its own ideas, formulates its assessments and beliefs independently, finds its own solution to the problem and supports it with reasonable, valid and convincing arguments. Critical thinking has a social character, since every thought is tested when it is shared with others. The pupil's own active life position is especially evident when comparing previous knowledge and concepts with newly obtained ones. There are various forms of work that involve the development of students' critical thinking: essays, essay-reasoning, discussion, dialogue, role play, etc. A special place is occupied by research technology, where students enter a high level of cognition, independent activity and development of a new problem vision, mastering of research procedures. A generalized basic model within the framework of the study is the model of learning as a creative search: from the vision and formulation of the problem to the hypothesis advancement, their verification, cognitive reflection on the results and process of cognition. Variants of the research model are game modeling, discussion, interviewing, solving problematic problems, etc.

A quick internet search for newspaper headlines shows that some forms of scary stories related to mobile technology appear every month, from textual language, which destroys our

³ O.N. Anyushenkova, Developing English reading, writing, grammar and integrated skills through using language learning technologies // Fundamental and applied research: topical issues, achievements and innovations. Collection of articles of the VI International scientific-practical conference. p. 299-302. 2017.

⁴ Gromova O. A. «Audiovisual method and practice of its application». M., 1977. – 150 s.

ability to use “real” language, to smartphones that are a source of distraction in the audience. There may also be general fatigue with respect to “another new technology in the audience”, or perhaps fear that the device will be more exciting than the lesson itself, and will become a kind of distraction. In addition, according to V.A. Travnev ⁵, when using these technologies, the following didactic principles of learning are implemented:

1. the principle of visibility - it is possible to visualize various concepts, some abstract patterns and models when using information and communication technologies;

2. the principle of accessibility and feasibility - the technologies under consideration open up fundamentally new opportunities in the implementation of this principle, since modern programmes make it possible to generate tasks of increasing difficulty;

3. the principle of individualization of education - modern technologies open up the possibility for each student to build an individual learning path. The advantage of modern technology and alternative information is that the process of its perception is always individualized, the student can assimilate it in a convenient mode and pace, it assumes the presence of significant motivation, because students watch only what is interesting and attracts attention;

4. the principle of consciousness - the student with the help of modern technology better can organize their training;

5. the principle of activity - the use of innovative technologies is coherent with the student's independent activity in finding the necessary information on the Internet.

Summing up, it should be noted that in order to use new opportunities for mobile learning in the educational process, organizational, research and methodological work is needed to introduce modern strategies, forms and methods of mobile learning into the educational process. For the modern digital generation of students, it is necessary to develop such technologies that would harmoniously use the benefits of traditional and information education. This problem is fully applicable to the teaching of a foreign language, the process to which should be aimed at improving both the foreign language communicative competence and the foreign language information competence necessary in the conditions of the new information society.

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⁵ V.A. Travnev, V.F. Gurkin, O.V. Travnev, “Distance learning and its development”, Moscow, p.28, 2008.